

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Socio-Cultural Factors Associated with Home Violence Against Women in Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Violence in the home is a major scourge in the society that needs unique attention to combat. There is a general saying that “a happy mind gives strength to the whole body” which means a happy woman makes a happy home, while a happy home makes a happy society. To this end, violence as a negative condition to the well-being of women is purely devastating to their happiness especially when it occurs within the home. This paper therefore explored survey design method technique in finding out the socio-cultural factors associated with home violence as experienced by women and its effects in Oye Ekiti, a town in Ekiti State of Nigeria. In a convenient sampling technique, data were collected from 200 married women who responded to questionnaire. Hypotheses were tested using chi-square. Results showed that factors such as level of education, religion belief and income were mostly among others not associated with violence in the home, which means there are more underlying factors to look out for. It was therefore recommended that government should incite stricter laws in addressing home violence cases family courts should also be put in place early warning systems to become aware of the consequences of ill-treatment of women at home. Also, religious organization should be more proactive in the teaching of morals towards curbing home violence.

Keywords: Violence; Home; Socio-Cultural Factors; Husbands; Women

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1.Introduction

Violence towards women is a salient condition and human rights issue. In the main, at least one out of five of the world’s woman populace are being sexually or bodily abused with the aid of a man or guys at some time in their existence (WHO,2010) Many, which include Oriola pregnant ladies and younger girls, are subject to severe, sustained or repeated attacks at their various homes by their spouses (World Development Report, 1993). These acts could culminate in psychological sexual or physical harm, or to women. It may also consist of threats, arbitrary deprivation of liberty or coercion in public or personal relations. Home violence encapsulates, however is never restricted to, “physical, sexual and psychological violence going on in the family, consisting of battering, sexual abuse of women (UNICEF,2000). Violence against women in view of this very study is a manifestation of traditionally unequal power relations between man and women within family context. This

have from time led to domination over and discrimination against women by men and to the prevention of the full advancement of women...” which has its origins in the patriarchal shape that oppresses female (Agbo & Choji.2014). As an institutional response, global, regional and country wide businesses have taken full size steps toward kingdom action to get rid of violence in opposition to women. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), adopted in 1979 by way of the UN General Assembly, is the international consignment of rights for women. This happens to be the first international mechanism, to outline violence against women and to set an agenda for national motion to end such a discrimination (Temilola(2015) Violence in opposition to women is a phenomena and social hassle that is found in each and every country, slicing throughout boundaries of class, culture, income, education, income, age and ethnicity.